

Effect of Surfactants on 1,2-Dichloroethane-in-Water Droplet Impacts at Electrified Liquid-Liquid Interface

Abdelatif Laroui^a, Karolina Kwaczyński^a, Monika Dąbrzalska^b, Martina Zatloukalova^c, Jan Vacek^c, Lukasz Poltorak^{a*}

^aDepartment of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, Electroanalysis and Electrochemistry Group, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Lodz, Tamka 12, 91-403 Lodz, Poland

^bDepartment of General Biophysics, Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, University of Lodz, Pomorska 141/143, 90-236 Lodz, Poland

^cDepartment of Medical Chemistry and Biochemistry, Faculty of Medicine and Dentistry, Palacky University, Hnevotinska 3, 775 15 Olomouc, Czech Republic

*Corresponding author: lukasz.poltorak@chemia.uni.lodz.pl

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Abstract

In this work, we used the electrified liquid-liquid interface (eLLI) to study the fusion of oil-in-water organic droplets (soft particles) upon coming into contact with the soft interface. Our focus was to define the effect of the neutral (1-tetradodecanol) and ionic (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and sodium dodecylsulfonate) surfactants that stabilize the colloidal solution on the electroanalytical output of the impact events. The electrochemically and interfacially active salt used in our work (tetramethylammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate) was always initially dissolved in the organic phase droplets. When the potential drop at the interface was set below the formal Galvani potential of the tetramethylammonium cation ion transfer, we observed ionic current events upon the fusion of the droplets at the eLLI, as studied by chronoamperometry. This phenomenon was found to be severely affected by the surfactants. Our system was investigated with several methods, including cyclic voltammetry, chronoamperometry, interfacial tension measurements, and finally zeta potential and droplet size distribution measurements based on dynamic light scattering.

1. Introduction

Impact electrochemistry is still an emerging field that aims to study, characterize, and detect the collision between individual particles that are suspended in solution with a signal-transducing element, typically the surface of a solid electrode [1,2], and recently the electrified liquid-liquid interface (eLLI) [3]. Most commonly, the impact events are studied with chronoamperometry. Quantitative analysis of current spikes attributed to the interaction

between the particle and the electrode surface can provide information about the particle size, type, chemical properties (*e.g.* catalytic properties), reaction kinetics, or even their content (the latter applied for soft objects that can undergo fusion and cargo release). This methodology has been used to investigate “solid” and “soft” particles [3].

Several reviews are available in which the current state of the art about impact electrochemistry is summarized and discussed [4,5]. There are a few possible origins for the electrochemical signals generated when the particle is located at the transducing surface: (i) direct faradaic impacts which involve electron transfer; (ii) mediated faradaic impacts, in which the colliding particle functions as a catalyst or mediator for the transfer of electrons; (iii) partial blockage of the electrode surface and inhibition of charge transfer reactions; (iv) a capacitive impact produced by the displacement of electric double layers [6]; (v) fusion of the soft particle followed by interfacial ion transfer reaction; and/or (vi) electron transfer across the liquid-liquid interface (LLI) catalyzed by particle impacts [3]. The latter two examples can only be studied using the platform known as the interface between two immiscible electrolyte solutions (ITIES) [3].

Compared to an electrode-solution interface, ITIES provides superior surface reproducibility (given by the self-organizing properties of the solvent molecules), as it is renewable and can be used to monitor interfacial ion transfer reactions. These properties were found to be especially useful for studying the impact of soft particles fusing over a soft junction. To our knowledge, the first report showing that 1,2-dichloroethane (1,2-DCE) emulsion droplets (DCE-in-water) fusion can occur at the polarized ITIES was done by the group of Kakiuchi [7]. They have shown that the ITIES could be emulsified upon application of the

Galvani potential difference, at the same time noticing that the presumable droplets fusion leads to the formation of “unusual” current spikes in the recorded current-potential dependencies. In his works, Kakiuchi *et al.* introduced and elaborated the term “electrochemical instability”, which refers to the unusual current spikes recorded at the ITIES in the presence of ionic surface-active molecules [8–11]. Laborda *et al.* [12] significantly improved the methodology of impact electrochemistry at ITIES by precise control of the composition of the DCE-in-water droplets, whereas Samec and Marecek further elaborated this concept [13,14]. Recent work by Huang *et al.* proved that ITIES can be used to follow the fusion and release of the cargo carried by liposomes [15]. As a model cargo, they used dopamine, K^+ , and Na^+ ions that were undergoing a facilitated interfacial ion transfer reaction after liposome fusion at the ITIES in the presence of crown ether dissolved in the organic phase.

Surfactants are molecules that contain a hydrophilic group that can hold a positive or negative charge, can be zwitterionic or neutral, and a hydrophobic region that can be made out of *e.g.* long chain hydrocarbons [16]. The intrinsic properties attributed to these molecules allow for their self-assembly at phase junctions *e.g.* air/water, or oil/water. These molecules are also used to stabilize emulsion droplets, and hence, their effect on the soft particles impact at the ITIES is expected to be crucial. There is a lack of understanding of how these molecules affect oil droplet fusion upon impact with electrified LLI. This knowledge can be directly translated into the interaction happening at the cell membrane, since ITIES-based systems can be considered as a biomimetic interface that can be studied with a range of electrochemical techniques. Not only do the intrinsic properties of the liquid-liquid interface resemble half of the lipid bilayer (the interfacial regions of the aqueous and the organic phase can be considered

as a primitive model of the polar and apolar part of the lipid bilayer, respectively) but also serve as a locus for the spontaneous formation of lipid monolayers [17].

Many research teams have studied the permeability of the lipid monolayers formed at the ITIES using a range of electroanalytical techniques [18–21]. One of the key findings by Konturri was that lateral compression is needed to form a compact lipid monolayer, otherwise rafts and island-like domains are formed [22].

As such, in this work, electroanalytical methods (cyclic voltammetry and chronoamperometry), interfacial tension measurements, zeta potential and dynamic light scattering size distribution studies were performed to evaluate the effect of the cationic (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide), anionic (sodium dodecyl sulfate) and neutral (tetradodecanol) surfactants used to stabilize the oil-in-water emulsion on oil droplet fusion at the electrified LLI (eLLI). The study was performed at a macroscopic ITIES, since the diameters of the particle droplets were higher than a few micrometers and could be easily detected in a system prone to significant capacitive current.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Chemicals

All chemicals were used as received unless stated otherwise. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, 364.45 g/mol, Sigma Aldrich); sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, 288.38 g·mol⁻¹, Sigma Aldrich), and 1-tetradecanol (TD, 214.393 g·mol⁻¹, Sigma Aldrich) were used as the surface-active species. Sodium chloride (NaCl, 58.44 g·mol⁻¹, Sigma Aldrich) was used as the aqueous phase electrolyte, whereas bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate (BTPPATPBCl; prepared using BTPPACl, M = 574.03 g·mol⁻¹, KTPBCl,

M = 496.11 g·mol⁻¹, both from Sigma–Aldrich) was employed as the organic phase background electrolyte [23]. 1,2-Dichloroethane (1,2-DCE, Sigma-Aldrich) served as the organic phase solvent. The salt tetramethylammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate (TMATPBCl) was dissolved in the organic phase droplets during impact experiments and was prepared by metathesis reaction between equimolar (1:1 mixtures) solutions of tetramethylammonium chloride (TMACl, 109.6 g·mol⁻¹, Acros Organics) and KTPBCl, in a methanol/water mixture (2/1; v/v), followed by recrystallization from acetone. Its purity was checked using ion transfer voltammetry after dissolving TMATPBCl in the organic phase. All aqueous solutions were prepared with ultra-pure water (18.2 MWcm).

2.2. Emulsion formulation

DCE in water emulsions were prepared by adding 100 µl of 10 mM TMATPBCl in 1,2-DCE solution into 4 mL of aqueous solution of 10 mM NaCl. The resulting mixture was sonicated for 10 s using a Q500 ultrasonic processor with a microtip probe (500 watts, 30% amplitude). The surfactants were added to the aqueous phase, and their concentration was subject to change (experimental variable). We found that the emulsion formed without surfactant had poor stability and the phases stratified after only a few minutes. As expected, the addition of surfactants significantly improved the stability of the emulsion, but limited its utility to a few hours. Due to this observation, all emulsions were used directly after the sonication step. It also must be underlined that after the addition of emulsion aliquot to the electrochemical cell the concentration of TMATPBCl in the droplets remains at 10 mM, whereas the concentration of free surfactant (non-adsorbed to the oil-in-droplet liquid-liquid interface) was diluted to micromolar level.

2.3. Methods

Electrochemical measurements were carried out using an Autolab 302n and a four-electrode glass cell with two Luggin capillaries (see **Fig. 1**). Two platinum electrodes were used as counter electrodes, and two Ag/AgCl wires served as reference electrodes. Particle size distribution and zeta potential measurements were done with a Zetasizer instrument from Malvern. The size distribution was measured immediately after emulsification. The average zeta potential of the emulsion droplets was determined by performing three measurements. Interfacial tension measurements of the DCE/water interface in the presence of CTAB, SDS, and TD were conducted using a drop-shape analyzer (ThetaFlex from Biolin Scientific). During the interfacial tension measurements, a borosilicate cuvette containing the aqueous phase was placed parallel to a light-emitting diode in a holder. The organic oil droplet was extruded from the treated syringe *via* a needle placed in the aqueous phase. The droplet volume was approx. 10 μ l. A camera was employed to obtain an image of the drop, which was further analyzed in the software AttensionOne. All measurements were done at room temperature.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Electroanalytical study of surfactants

Fig. 1A shows a four-electrode cell that was used to study the interfacial behavior of the employed surfactants, the impact of bare DCE-in-water emulsion droplets, and the impacts of droplets further modified with surfactant molecules. We first studied the influence of the surfactant concentration present either in the aqueous (CTAB or SDS) or in the organic (TD) phase on the resulting current potential dependency. The employed cell scheme is shown in **Fig. 1B**; see surfactant initial phase, electrolytes, and employed electrodes.

Figure 1. Scheme of electrochemical cell employed during electrochemical measurements along with chemical structures of surfactants on the top right (A). Cell scheme used to study interfacial behavior of surfactants at ITIES (B) and cell scheme used to study soft particle impacts at ITIES (C). RE and CE are the reference and counter electrodes, respectively. x , y and z are experimental variables.

Fig. 2 shows the cyclic voltammograms (CVs) recorded in the presence of three different surfactants either initially present in the aqueous (SDS – **Fig. 2A** or CTAB – **Fig. 2C**) or the organic (TD – **Fig. 2D**) phase. When SDS was added to the aqueous phase, starting from a concentration equal to 10 μM , we were able to record a pair of signals with a half-wave potential equal to 0.02 V. According to convention, the negative signal is due to SDS transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase (the positive signal is its back transfer). In the concentration range from 10 μM to 100 μM , the CVs exhibited reversible charge transfer characteristics, (i) with positive and negative current intensities increasing linearly with the

SDS concentration (see the calibration curve shown in **Fig. 2B**), and (ii) the intensity ratio of both signals approaching unity (the ratio of the positive to the negative slope from **Fig. 2B** is 0.99). As the concentration of SDS was further increased to 250 μM , 500 μM , and 1 mM, abnormal current-potential characteristics occurred, as shown in **Fig. S1-A** (see **ESI**). The occurrence of occasional current spikes may indicate LLI destabilization. **Fig. 2C** shows the set of analogical data obtained in the presence of CTAB added to the aqueous phase. For the cationic surfactant, we did not observe the reversible ion transfer characteristics as also shown in other already published works [24,25]. Instead, only positive irregular current patterns with abrupt drops were found in the potential range from -0.3 V to 0.1 V up to $[\text{CTAB}] = 100 \mu\text{M}$. Interestingly, for $[\text{CTAB}] \gg 250 \mu\text{M}$ (see **Fig. S1-B** in **ESI**), the potential window is limited by (i) the positive current reaching around 450 μA for 250 μM CTAB or 650 μA for the 1 mM CTAB, and (ii) a number of sharp current spikes appearing at $E > -0.1 \text{ V}$. Finally, **Fig. 2D** shows three CVs recorded in the presence of the neutral TD initially present in the organic phase at a concentration up to 5 mM. Here, the voltammetric features seem to be unaffected by the surfactant addition, indicating its electrochemical (interfacial) inactivity. Our observations are in line with the studies of Kakiuchi *et al.*: (i) irregular current spikes appear when the transfer of ionic surfactant occurs across the electrified LLI – this phenomenon was termed electrochemical instability [9,26]. (ii) In cyclic voltammograms, current fluctuations appeared in the vicinity of the half-wave potential of the surfactant ion transfer, as was found for anionic surfactants (alkanesulfonate and alkyl sulfate salts) [8,10,27], cationic surfactants (decylamine) [8,11], and alkaline-earth metal ions complexing agents (Triton X-405) [28]. (iii) Also, irregular current spikes were dependent on scan rate and concentration [27]. In our work, we would like

to give additional attention to the correlation between the occurrence of current spikes and the critical micelle concentration (*cmc*) determined from the interfacial tension measurements.

Figure 2. Cyclic voltammograms (CVs) recorded for increasing concentrations (10; 20; 30; 40; 50; 60; 80 and 100 μM) of SDS (A), Calibration curve plotted based on positive and negative current intensities as a function of SDS concentration (B), selected CVs recorded in the presence of CTAB (30; 40; 50; 60; 80 and 100 μM) in the aqueous phase (C), CVs for 1-tetradecanol at different concentrations. The aqueous phase was 10 mM NaCl. The polarization direction was towards positive potential during the forward scan. The scan rate was set to $20 \text{ mV} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

3.2. Interfacial tension measurements

To further understand the behavior of the selected surfactants at the polarized LLI, interfacial tension (γ) measurements were performed using a drop-shape analyzer. The effect of surfactant (SDS, CTAB or TD) concentration on interfacial tension (γ) was studied for three different LLI compositions: (i) bare ITIES (10 mM NaCl // 5 mM BTPPATPBCl); (ii) with [TMACl] = 5 mM additionally present in the aqueous phase; and (iii) with [TMATPBCl] = 5 mM added to the organic phase. **Fig. 3A** shows a scheme indicating the composition of the aqueous and the organic phase used for γ measurements. **Fig. 3B** shows γ measurements at the LLI in the presence of CTAB. As expected, the γ of the LLI in the presence and the absence of TMACl started to decrease progressively with increasing CTAB concentration. The γ dropped at around 10 μ M, and started stabilizing (indicating the formation of a complete surfactant monolayer, and the formation of micelles) at a few mM. The calculated (or apparent) CMC values were found to be dependent on the composition of the aqueous and organic phase. We found that these were equal to: (i) 2.5 mM at a bare LLI; and (ii) 2.7 mM with [TMACl] = 5 mM added to the aqueous phase were derived from the recorded dependencies (see Fig. 3B). Also, the order of magnitude of the CMC is consistent with the high frequency of current spikes that started appearing on CVs recorded in the presence of CTAB at similar concentrations (see **Fig. S1B**). According to Kakiuchi *at al.*, and based on our understanding, the observed “electrochemical instability” can be governed by (i) the Marangoni movement of surface-active species over planar LLI, (ii) local emulsification facilitated by the surface-active species, and (iii) micelles impacting and fusing at the electrified LLI. Although it is assumed that the Gibbs free energy of the ion transferring from one phase to another is equal to the energy needed to deprive the ion of the solvation shell in the first phase and establishment of the solvation shell

in the second phase, this process may be incomplete, especially for large molecules and amphiphiles. As such, one can imagine that upon the ion transfer and especially at $\Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi \gg \Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi'_{ion^{+/-}}$, ions will start crossing the interface along with the solvent molecules, leading to interfacial emulsification. Stratification in turn can be observed as current spikes.

When TMAPBCl salt was added to the organic phase, the γ drop was shifted from around 10 μM (red and black lines with **Fig. 3B**) to 12 mM (blue line from **Fig. 3B**) and dropped abruptly from 30 $\text{mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ to 5 $\text{mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ (in contrast, in the absence of the TMAPBCl the γ drop spanned a few concentration orders of magnitude). This suggests that below a CTAB concentration equal to a few mM, interfacial adsorption does not occur. This is an interesting result as one would expect the ion exchange reaction in which TMA^+ from the organic phase will be replaced by the CTA^+ initially present in the aqueous phase to happen. The obtained discrepancy can be explained by the fact that the addition of TMAPBCl leads to LLI polarization ($\Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi > 0V$), which may prevent cationic surfactant adsorption, and eventually when the $\Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi > \Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi'_{TMA^+}$ the transfer of TMA^+ from the organic phase to the aqueous phase also will be restrained. Such behavior was not observed for an anionic surfactant, since for all the studied LLI formulations the patterns of γ plotted as a function of [SDS] followed similar courses (in all cases, γ started to decrease at around 100 μM and reached a plateau at around [SDS] = 4 mM). Interfacial potential difference can be deduced from the Nernst-like equation for the ion transfer reaction:

$$\Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi = \Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi'_{TMA^+} + 0.059 \log \frac{a_{TMA^+}^{org}}{a_{TMA^+}^{aq}} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi$ is the Galvani potential difference set across the ITIES, $\Delta_{org}^{aq} \phi'_{TMA^+}$ is the formal Galvani potential difference of the TMA^+ ion transfer (160 mV) [29], the value 0.059 is derived

from treatments of physicochemical constants, whereas $a^{\text{org/aq}}$ stands for the activity of TMA^+ in the organic and the aqueous phase, respectively. In our case, the $a_{\text{TMA}^+}^{\text{org}} \gg a_{\text{TMA}^+}^{\text{aq}}$, meaning that the entire $0.059 \log \frac{a_{\text{TMA}^+}^{\text{org}}}{a_{\text{TMA}^+}^{\text{aq}}}$ will be positive, and hence, $\Delta_{\text{org}}^{\text{aq}} \phi$ will have a positive value. As such, the shift in the γ of the LLI in the presence of TMAPBCl in the organic phase, and CTAB added to the aqueous phase, towards higher CTAB concentrations is not surprising. The positively charged molecules/micelles should be repelled from the interfacial region when the above configuration is utilized. The eventual transfer of CTA^+ from the aqueous to the organic phase (exchange reaction with the TMA^+ from the organic phase) requires additional energetic input first to disturb the micelle structure (present in the aqueous phase at the studied concentration), overcompensate interfacial adsorption and finally transfer from the aqueous to the organic phase. This indicates that the interfacial polarization should be taken into account when similar experiments are performed. For TD, the γ remained constant even at high concentrations, indicating that at a mM concentration level we are not approaching the CMC values (data not shown).

Figure 3. Schemes prepared to indicate the composition of the aqueous and the organic phase used for interfacial tension measurement (A). Interfacial tension measurements for (B) CTAB and (C) SDS at different aqueous and organic phase compositions.

Table 1 summarizes all CMC values measured using a drop shape analyzer. Additional values from the literature were included for comparison. One should note that the presence of electrolytes either in the aqueous or in the organic phase can affect the readings when interfacial tension measurements are used for the CMC calculations [30,31].

Table1. CMC values determined by interfacial measurements and reported values from the literature.

CMC (mM)/Surfactants	Bare ITIES	TMA ⁺ in the (aq)	TMA ⁺ in the (org)	Literature
CTAB	2.5	2.7	12	0,9-1,07 [30,32–

35]

3.3. Impact experiments in the presence of surfactants

Chronoamperometric measurements were performed to assess the effect of the surfactant type (used to stabilize the emulsion droplets) on the impact events. To do so, we followed the protocols published by Laborda *et al.* and Trojanek *et al.* [12,13]. We used an electrochemical cell with a high surface area (100 mm²). Being aware that eLLI placed in such a cell provides a significant amount of capacitive contribution, we focused on multiple fusion events (ensured by the appropriate amount of DCE-in-water emulsion added to the aqueous phase), and assessed the effect of the addition of the ionic surfactants. The electrochemically active salt TMAPBCl, which ensures unidirectional current transients during impact events, was always initially dissolved in the organic phase droplet. To observe the current spikes, the Galvani potential difference applied across the eLLI was held below $\Delta_{org}^{aq} \Phi'_{TMA^+}$, facilitating the transfer of the TMA⁺ from the organic to the aqueous phase. **Fig. 4** shows chronoamperograms recorded in the presence of DCE-in-water droplets (10 mM TMAPBCl) and droplets stabilized with surface-active species (CTAB, SDS or TD). The addition of surfactants with charged and/or polar head groups will significantly increase the droplets' surface hydrophilicity, and consequently their interactions with the organic phase. **Fig. 4A** was recorded shortly after the addition of a bare DCE-in-water emulsion. A number of current spikes recorded for the given system are attributed to the direct fusion of multiple DCE-in-water droplets. Dynamic light scattering analysis revealed that the size of these droplets was initially found to be in the range from around 500 nm up to a few μm (see **Fig. S2 from ESI**). We also noticed that droplets without surfactant rapidly agglomerated, forming bigger objects, which also could

contribute to the current patterns, especially for prolonged experiments. Furthermore, the average diameter (d) of a droplet was estimated using the equation below [12]:

$$d = 2 \left(\frac{3Q}{4\pi Fc} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (2),$$

where $c = 10$ mM ($10000 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) is the concentration of TMATPBCl dissolved in the impacting droplet; F is the Faraday constant, and Q is the charge measured during the impact event. By integrating the area under the current transients, the Q value was obtained and then substituted into eq. (2). The obtained values were in the range from $1.4 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $4.97 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, indicating that in addition to multiple impact events, we were most likely able to record the fusion of a single droplet. Having proof that a macroscopic eLLI can be used to follow impact events, we moved on to other three emulsions, stabilized with cationic, anionic, and neutral surfactants. **Fig. 4B–D** shows the data set for two different concentrations of the surfactant molecules used during formulation studies. Basically, a 0.5 mM surfactant solution was used to prepare an emulsion of $100 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ DCE added to 4 ml of the aqueous phase. The resulting concentration is high enough to fully cover the oil droplet surface, and at the same time should be low enough to avoid the formation of micelles. This was also observed with DLS-based size distribution, since small particles with the dimensionally of micelles were not observed. Also, the voltammograms recorded before and after the addition of the emulsion droplets stabilized with surfactants did not reveal any voltammetric features characteristic of electrochemical instability (especially CTAB and SDS, as shown in **Fig. 1**). This means that the concentration of free surfactant molecules or their micelles in the bulk aqueous phase, if not negligible, is significantly below a few μM . This was further demonstrated by measuring the zeta potential values of emulsions that contain different concentrations of CTAB and SDS added to bare

droplets (see **Fig. S3 in the ESI**). The zeta potential value for surfactant non-modified bare droplets was found to be around -47 mV. Once CTAB was added to the emulsion solution, charge reversal occurred even for the lowest studied concentration (this is around 25 mV for 50 μ M CTAB). Further addition of the cationic surfactant ensured a zeta potential increase up to [CTAB] = 5 mM. Above this value, zeta potential remained nearly constant, which could indicate that the surface of the organic phase droplets is saturated and micelle formation may be triggered. A similar trend was observed for the SDS surfactant; however the zeta potential values, as expected, decreased (or increased if absolute values are considered) as a function of the negatively charged surfactant concentration. For a given system, saturation was also observed for [SDS] > 5 mM. For clarity, the zeta potential values of the oil-in-water emulsion plotted as a function of [CTAB] and [SDS] are summarized in **Fig. S4 in the ESI**. A surfactant concentration of 0.5 mM was chosen to stabilize the emulsion, since within this range micelle formation should not occur, and the zeta potential was equal to -46.6 mV for bare droplets (10 mM TMAPBCl), 63.2 mV, -57.6 mV and -44.4 mV droplets covered with CTAB, SDS, and TD, respectively. When emulsions stabilized with different surfactants were added to the aqueous phase of the eLLI cell, we found that the current spikes only appeared in the presence of SDS. Our findings can be summarized as: (i) the applied eLLI configuration and its polarization ensures the accumulation of positive charge on the organic phase side of the LLI, which should electrostatically attract negatively charged droplets. This was found to be true for bare and SDS-stabilized emulsions. In **Fig. 4C**, one can notice a current spikes pattern with a very high impact frequency (0.52 Hz), comparable to the one we calculated for the bare droplets (0.73 Hz). The electrostatic attraction between the positively charged organic side of the

interface and negatively charged emulsion droplets probably contributes to a negative emulsion entropy that causes fusion events. (ii) We were unable to record clear current events when the oil droplets were stabilized with TD (a neutral surfactant). Even though the obtained size distribution of the organic phase droplets was comparable to three other configurations (the average d was 871 nm) and the zeta potential had a significant negative value, the application of positive polarization did not result in the appearance of a number of current spikes. In turn, we noticed a few signals that were used to calculate the diameter of the particles (these were found in the range of 0.83 μm to 1.66 μm). Signals started appearing at lower potential values, at which positive polarization of the organic phase increased. This means that the energy needed to disrupt a stable emulsion system (TD based) needs to be much higher than for bare or oil droplets stabilized with SDS (see **Fig. S5 from ESI**). Also, at this point, we can postulate that TD-covered emulsion droplets increase their surface hydrophilicity and decrease the probability of the fusion event. (iii) We also observed a set of data for the CTAB-based emulsion. As indicated in **Fig. 4B**, the addition of CTAB-stabilized DCE-in-water emulsion droplets does not give any current spikes, in accordance with the electrostatic repulsion of the positively charged droplets and positively charged organic side of the interface. Positive current transients started appearing in recorded CA curves for an applied Galvani potential difference that was higher than around 0.2 V. Since the transfer of TMA^+ from the organic phase to the aqueous phase can only occur when $\Delta_{org}^{aq} \Phi < \Delta_{org}^{aq} \Phi'_{\text{TMA}^+}$, and the bulk concentration of $[\text{TMA}^+]_{\text{aq}}$ is close to 0 (electrochemically negligible amounts of TMA^+ may partition into the aqueous phase from the added oil droplets) the recorded current spikes were attributed to the transfer of CTA^+ . High values of applied potential difference will eventually lead to charge

reversal at the eLLI, inhibiting the CTA^+ -stabilized emulsion from fusing over. In that case, the impacts are not followed by the transfer of TMA^+ to the aqueous phase, but the transfer of CTA^+ to the organic phase. The reported data show that the surface charge of the studied objects, in this case DCE-in-water emulsion, significantly affects droplet fusion and impacts. One should also assume that hydrophobic interactions should facilitate fusion events, since hydrophobic emulsion droplets should be attracted by the organic phase side of the LLI. However, as was reported by Wang *et al.* [37], the presence of a significant amount of charge at the surface of two entities, *i.e.* particles and interfaces, can significantly decrease the number of hydrophobic interactions.

Figure 4. Chronoamperograms recorded after the addition of DCE-in-water emulsion (bare or stabilized with surfactants) to the aqueous phase compartment of the electrochemical cell. The concentration of TMATPBCl in the organic phase droplet was set to 10 mM. (A) current spikes of oil droplets with no added surfactant. The remaining graphs were recorded for the following conditions: (B) 0.5 mM CTAB; (C) 0.5 mM SDS, (D) 0.5 mM TD. The concentration of the surfactants is given for the initial emulsion formation. The applied Galvani potential difference was -0.1V.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we studied the effect of the cationic, anionic, and neutral surfactants used to stabilize DCE in a water emulsion on droplets impact events at the polarized liquid-liquid interface. To do so, the interfacial behavior of all surface-active molecules was first studied at the electrified liquid-liquid interface using voltammetry and interfacial tension measurements. It was found that the micelle surface charge affected by the polar head group of the molecules used, as well as the value of the applied Galvani potential difference, severely affect oil droplet impact events (at the electrified liquid-liquid interface) as followed by chronoamperometry.

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Data availability statement

Data published in this manuscript were uploaded to Zenodo repository (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10871182).

Conflict of interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest

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